

BUXORO VOHASI AYOLLARINING AN'ANAVIY BOSH KIYIMLARI- DO'PPI VA RO'MOL

Yarashova Mohlaroyim Shuxrat qizi

Sa'dullayev Umid Shokirovich

Yo'ldosheva Feruza Yashin qizi

Osiyo xalqaro universiteti o'qituvchilari.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680851>

Annatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Buxoro vohasi ayollarining an'anaviy bosh kiyimlari, ularning turlari, shuningdek turli marosimlarda va kundalik turmushda kiyiladigan bosh kiyimlari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: do'ppi, ro'mol, peshonaband, ro'moli pulakchi.

ТРАДИЦИОННЫЙ ГОЛОВНОЙ УБОР ЖЕНЩИН БУХАРСКОГО ОАЗИСА - КАПЮШОН И НАШИВКА

Аннотация. В статье даны краткие сведения о традиционных головных уборах женщин Бухарского оазиса, их видах, а также о головных уборах, которые носили во время различных обрядов и в повседневной жизни.

Ключевые слова: тюрбетейка, платок, повязка на голову, мужчина в платке.

TRADITIONAL HEADWEAR OF WOMEN OF THE BUKHARA OASIS - HOOD AND KERF

Abstract. This article gives a brief information about the traditional hats of women of the Bukhara oasis, their types, history of origin, as well as hats worn in various ceremonies and everyday life.

Keywords: doppi, rumol, peshanaband, rumoli pulakchi.

O'zbek milliy liboslari qadim davrlardan beri maqtovg'a sazovor bo'lib kelgan va o'zbek madaniyati rivoj topgan ayni hozirgi davrda alohida ahamiyatga ega bo'lmoqda. Aholi an'anaviy kiyim-kechaklari-o'rganilish jihatdan dolzarb masalalardan hisoblanadi. Xususan, Buxoro vohasi aholisi maishiy turmush tarzining bevosita ajralmas bo'lagi sifatida ushbu soha etnograf olimlarning diqqat markazida turadi.

Ayollar bosh kiyimlari odatda, ikkiga bo'lingan: boshga kiyiladigan kiyimlar: qalpoq, do'ppi (kallapo'sh), quloqchin va boshga o'raladigan yoki yopinadigan ro'mol, peshonaband, lachak, durra, durraband, lokki va h.k.¹

Ayollarning an'anaviy bosh kiyimlari kiyim egasining oiladagi mavqeini aniq ifodalagan.

¹ Дониёров А, Бўриев О, Аширов А. Марказий Осиё халклари этнографияси, этногези ва этник тарихи. - Т.: "Янги нашр", 2011, - Б.92.

CHunonchi, bosh kiyim va soch turmagiga qarab qiz bolani turmushga chiqqan kelindan, yosh onani farzandsiz ayoldan, o'rta yoshli ayollarni esa kekxa momolardan farqlash mumkin bo'lgan. O. A. Suxareva² T. G.Emelyanenko³, N. P. Lobacheva⁴lar o'z asarlaridan Buxoro vohasi kiyimlari shu jumladan , ayollarning an'anaviy kundalik va marosim bosh kiyimlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berib o'tishgan.

Ayollar milliy liboslarini milliy bosh kiyimlarsiz tasavvur qilib bo'lmaydi. XIX asr oxiri XX asr boshlarida O'rta Osiyoning boshqa hududlarida bo'lgani singari, Buxoroda ham do'ppi va ro'mol asosiy ayollar bosh kiyimi bo'lgan.

Ko'p joylarda, xususan qishloqlarda bosh kiyim yoshiga qarab har xil bo'lgan. Qiz bolalar do'ppi kiyib yurishgan. Samarqand, Urgut va uning tevarak atrofidagi qishloqlarda keng tarqalgan do'ppilar tog'lik tojik va Markaziy Osiyo yahudiy qizlari do'ppisiga o'xshagan yumaloq ko'rinishda bo'lib, hozirda bunday do'ppilar yo'qolib ketgan.⁵

XX asrda qiz va juvonlar orasida dumaloq do'ppi keng tarqalgan. Ayollar do'ppisining sirti butunlay "o'rma", "xodo'zi" usulida kashtalangan. Bosh kiyim bilan bog'liq turli marosimlar ham bo'lgan. Masalan, to'y o'tgandan keyin do'ppi ustidan peshona durra - peshonaband bog'lab yurilgan. Birinchi farzand tug'ilgandan so'ng, do'ppi o'rniga ro'mol bog'lab yurishgan.

Ko'pincha, qo'shaloq ro'mol taqilgan. Birinchisi boshga shundoq tashlab, uchlarini orqaga yig'ib qo'yilgan. Ikkinchi ro'mol esa uning ustidan peshona bilan bog'langan.⁶

Buxoro yahudiyolari bosh kiyimlari orasida duppining duppi tos deb atagan oltin naqshli turi 1930-1940 yillarda saqlanib qolgan: ularni qizlar, yangi turmush qurgan ayollar bir yil yoki bola tug'ilguniga qadar kiyishgan, shuningdek kekxa ayollar diniy bayramlarda kiyishgan, ibodatxonaga borishda va uyda qizlar singari, ro'molsiz kiyishgan.⁷

Erondan kelgan payli – ro'moli pulakchi va to'qilgan matodan qilingan uchburchak sharflar ham ular uchun odatiy edi. Bunday sharfni to'y paytida kelin to'g'ridan-to'g'ri boshiga kiygan, yangi turmush qurganlar uni duppi tos ustiga kiyib, uchlarini iyak ostidan o'tqazib, bo'yin orqasiga bog'lashgan.

² O. A. Сухарева. История средне азиатского костюма Самарканд (2^яполовина XIX-начало XXв.).-Москва «Наука»,1982.

³ Емельяненко Т. Традиционный костюм бухарских евреев (проблемы этнокультурной идентичности).- Санкт-Петербург 2012.

⁴ Лобачева Н.П., Сазонова М.В. (ред.) Традиционная одежда народов Средней Азии и Казахстана.- Москва «Наука»,1989

⁵ Дониёров А, Бўриев О, Аширов А. Марказий Осиё халклари этнографияси, этногези ва этник тарихи.- Т.: "Янги нашр", 2011,- Б.93.

⁶ O. A. Сухарева . История средне азиатского костюма Самарканд (2^яполовина XIX-начало XXв.).-Москва «Наука»,1982,С.82.

⁷ Емельяненко Т. Традиционный костюм бухарских евреев (проблемы этнокультурной идентичности).- Санкт-Петербург 2012,- С.40.

Buxoro yahudiy ayollarining o'ziga xos ikki xil ro'mol o'rash usuli: pastki qismi - durra rumol - kichkina va peshonani yopib, baland bog'langan, yuqori sarband- ro'molning uchlari bo'yin va orqa tomondan bog'langan. Tojiklar va o'zbeklar uchun, aksincha, tepasi kichikroq ro'mol bo'lib, katta ro'molning uchlari ko'kragiga osilgan holda qoldirilgan yoki bir uchi orqaga tashlangan. Peshonaband zardo'zi naqshinkor ro'mollari durra ro'mol bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ular boy tojiklar va o'zbeklar tomonidan ishlatilgan bo'lsa-da, Buxoro yahudiylari orasida ham eng keng tarqalgan bo'lib, bugungi kunda yahudiy sozandlari - xalq musiqasi ijrochilarining deyarli majburiy bosh kiyimidir. Ro'mol kiyish Buxoro yahudiylari va qo'shni aholining XIX asr oxiri – XX asr boshlarida qizlarga xos liboslarining odatiy xususiyati edi. Ro'mol Buxoro-Samarqand vohasida odatdagidek bog'lanardi va tugunni boshning orqa tomoniga baland qilib qo'yishardi.⁸

Mazkur maqolada, Buxoro vohasi an'anaviy liboslarining ajralmas qismi hisoblangan ayollar milliy bosh kiyimlari mazkur mavzu yuzasidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar nuqtai nazaridan imkon qadar tahlil qilindi. Xalqning an'anaviy milliy tarixini o'rganish, xususan aholi ijtimoiy hayotining har bir detallarini o'rganib, tahlil qilish ushbu davrdagi etnografik tadqiqotlarning asosiy dolzarb muammolaridandir.

REFERENCES

1. O. A. Suxareva . Istoriya sredne aziatskogo kostyuma Samarkand (2^l polovina XIX-nachalo XXv.)-Moskva «Nauka»,1982.
2. Lobacheva N.P., Sazonova M.V. (red.) Traditsionnaya odejda narodov Sredney Azii i Kazaxstana.- Moskva «Nauka»,1989.
3. Doniyorov A,Bo'riev O,Ashirov A.Markaziy Osiyo xalqlari etnografiyasi, etnognezi va etnik tarixi.-T.:''YAngi nashr'',2011.
4. Emelyanenko Tatyana Grigorevna . Traditsionnyy kostyum buxarskix evreev (problemy etnokulturnoy identichnosti).Sankt-Peterburg 2012.
5. Ярашова, М. . (2024). ЖАҲОН ЭТНОЛОГИЯСИ ФАНИ ВА УНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ МЕТОДОЛОГИЯСИ. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(10), 362–368. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/44901>
6. Ярашова, М. (2024). БУХОРО ВОҲАСИДА МАТО ВА МАТО ТАЙЁРЛАШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(11), 782–787. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/48057>
7. Yarashova, M. (2024). ILK O'RTA ASR MANBALARIDA KIYIM-KECHAKLAR VA ULAR BILAN BOG'LIQ ATAMALAR TAVSIFI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12),

⁸ Емельяненко Т. Традиционный костюм бухарских евреев (проблемы этнокультурной идентичности).- Санкт-Петербург 2012,- С.41.

- 621–632. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58456>
8. Yarashova, M. (2024). ILK O'RTA ASR MANBALARIDA KIYIM-KECHAKLAR VA ULAR BILAN BOG'LIQ ATAMALAR TAVSIFI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 621–632. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58456>
9. Yuldosheva, F. (2024). MIRZO ULUG'BEK KUTUBXONASI VA BUGUNGI TAQDIRI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 741–749. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58564>
10. Yuldosheva, F. (2024). BOLA TUG'ILISHI BILAN BOG'LIQ MAROSIMLAR O'ZBEK XALQI HAYOTINING AJRALMAS QISMI SIFATIDA. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(11), 788–791. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/48058>
11. Yuldosheva, F. Y. qizi. (2023). LEV NIKOLAYEVICH GUMILYOVNING “QADIMGI TURKLAR” ASARIDA KO'KTURKLAR YODGORLIKLARI XUSUSIDA. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(16), 338–342. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/goldenbrain/article/view/3908>
12. Каримов, С. (2024). ОРДЕН НАКШБАНДИЯ: ИСТОРИЯ, УЧЕНИЕ И ВЛИЯНИЕ. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 548-555.
13. Yusupovich, K. S. (2024). Abu Hafs Kabir and the Spread of the Hanafi Madhhab in Transoxiana. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(9), 204-207.
14. Sadullayev U. (2024). MAHALLA: UNDERSTANDING THE CONCEPT. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(4), 376–385.
15. Sadullaev U. (2024). USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(5), 344–352.
16. Sadullaev, U. (2024). EDUCATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A NEW ERA OF OPPORTUNITY. *Medicine, Pedagogy and Technology: Theory and Practice*, 2(6), 238–241.
17. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). Media literacy is a requirement of the modern world. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 276-280.
18. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). Media literacy is a requirement of the modern world. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 276-280.

19. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). The Development of Culture and Art during the Timurid Era: the Development of Architecture and its Characteristics. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(9), 133-138.
20. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). The Development of Culture and Art during the Timurid Era: the Development of Architecture and its Characteristics. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(9), 133-138.
21. Sadullayev, U. (2024). EDWARD ALLWORTH AND THE STUDY OF MODERN UZBEKS. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 303-308.
22. Sadullayev, U. (2024). ETHNOGENESIS AND ETHNIC HISTORY OF THE UZBEK PEOPLE. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 355-361.
23. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2024). MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. MODERN SCIENCE, 2181, 3906.
24. Sadullayev, U. (2024). THE CONCEPT OF JADIDISM AND ITS ESSENCE. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 631-636.
25. Shokir o'g'li, S. U. (2023). The History of the Creation and Formation of the Neighborhood. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(10), 480-485.
26. SadullayevUmidjon Shokir O'g'li, . (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MAHALLA SYSTEM'S REFORMATIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(10), 25–30.
27. Shokir o'gli, S. U. (2023). The Essence of State Policy on Youth in New Uzbekistan. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(9), 554-559.
28. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN RAISING A SPIRITUALLY MATURE GENERATION. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 488–493.
29. Sadullayev, U. (2023). ABOUT THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NEIGHBORHOOD. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 722–727.
30. SadullayevUmidjon Shokir O'gli, . (2023). ELUCIDATION OF ISSUES OF THE HISTORY OF BUKHARA GUZARS IN O. A. SUKHAREVA AND HER STUDIES. International Journal Of History And Political Sciences, 3(11), 30–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue11-07>
31. Sadullayev, U. (2023). O'zbekistondaxotin-qizlargaberilayotgane'tibor: mahalla boshqaruvidaxotin-qizlarningroli. In Oriental Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 551-556). OOO «SupportScience».

32. Shokir o'gli, U. S. (2023). MILLIY QADRIYATLARIMIZ ASROVCHISI. Journal of new century innovations, 35(1), 79-80.
33. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 755–757.
34. Sadullayev, U. (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 132-135.
35. Toshpo‘latova, S., Gadayeva, M., & Sadullayev, U. (2024). SHARQ ALLOMALARINING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI. Modern Science and Research, 3(12), 985–993. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58746>
36. Haqqulov, M. Y. O. G. L. (2022). Markaziy Osiyoda ilk diplomatik munosabatlartarixi. Science and Education, 3(10), 385-389.
37. Yunusovich, H. M. (2024). Experiences Related to the Fine Fiber Cotton of Uzbekistan during the Years of Soviet Authority. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(9), 129-132.
38. Yunusovich, H. M. (2024). The Formation, Development and Role of the High Seljuk Empire Founded by the Turkic Peoples in the Islamic World. Miasto Przyszłości, 53, 956-959.
39. Ozodlikvamustaqillikg‘oyalarini, A. O ‘RTA OSIYO XALQLARINING OZODLIK ORZUSI BO‘LGAN “TURKISTON MUXTORIYATI” Haqqulov Mehridin Yunusovich.
40. Haqqulov, M. (2024). O ‘RTA OSIYO XALQLARINING OZODLIK ORZUSI BO‘LGAN “TURKISTON MUXTORIYATI”. Modern Science and Research, 3(12), 609-613.
41. PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN FOR FORMATION OF DEVELOPMENT FOR PREPARATION FOR UNIVERSITY. (2024). Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 4(5), 575-578. <https://mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/1502>
42. Haqqulov, M. Y. O. G. L. (2022). Markaziy Osiyoda ilk diplomatik munosabatlar tarixi. Science and Education, 3(10), 385-389.
43. Yunusovich, H. M. (2024). Experiences Related to the Fine Fiber Cotton of Uzbekistan during the Years of Soviet Authority. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 4(9), 129-132.
44. Yunusovich, H. M. (2024). The Formation, Development and Role of the High Seljuk Empire Founded by the Turkic Peoples in the Islamic World. Miasto Przyszłości, 53, 956-959.

45. Haqqulov, M. (2024). O 'RTA OSIYO XALQLARINING OZODLIK ORZUSI BO'LGAN "TURKISTON MUXTORIYATI". *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 609-613.
46. Рахмонова, С. (2024). HARMONY OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING. *Журналуниверсальных научных исследований*, 2(5), 366-375.
47. Ramatov, J., Hasanov, M., & Rahmonova, S. (2024). TA'LIM TIZIMI MODERNIZATSIYALASHUVINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY ASOSLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(8), 160-172.
48. Rahmonova, S. S. Q. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN MA'NAVIY-MADANIY ISLOHOTLAR DINAMIKASI VA SOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 3(2), 95-104.
49. Rahmonova Sanoat Shuhratqizi. (2024). SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS ARE THE FOUNDATION OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14503228>
50. Ярашова, М. (2025). ПАРАНЖИ ВА УНИНГ ЎРГАНИЛИШ ТАРИХИ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 160–168. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/60323>
51. Muyiddinov, B. (2023). XII-XIII ASRLAR DAVRIDA BUXORODA ILM – FANNING RIVOJLANISHI. *SCHOLAR*, 1(28), 341–345. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10027071>
52. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2023). MO'G'ULLAR BOSQINI DAVRIDA BUXORONING AYANCHLI TAQDIRI. *TADQIQOTLAR.UZ*, 25(2), 212–215. Retrieved from <http://tadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/new/article/view/308>
53. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2023). THE ROLE OF BUKHARA AND OTHER CITIES IN THE MILITARY ART AND ARMY STRUCTURE OF KHOREZMSHAHS . *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 35(3), 55–58. Retrieved from <https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/10035>
54. Muyiddinov, B. (2024). BARTHOLD'S "СОЧИНЕНИЯ. ТОМ I. ТУРКЕСТАН В ЭПОХУ МОНГОЛЬСКОГО НАШЕСТВИЯ" THE HISTORY OF THE CREATION OF THE WORK. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 3(1), 699–702. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10552555>
55. Muyiddinov, B. (2024). THE ROLE OF MILITARY REFORMS IN THE BUKHARA KHANATE IN THE LIFE OF THE STATE UNDER THE SHAYBANIDS. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 3(2), 646–648. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10668887>

56. MB Bahodir o'g'li. (2024). Military Art of Turkish Khaganate in the Early Middle Ages. *European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education*, 4(16), 223–227. <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/2705/2586>
57. XORAZMSHOHIDLAR DAVLATI HAYOTIDA TURKON XOTUNNING O'RNI. (2024). MEDICINE, PEDAGOGY AND TECHNOLOGY: THEORY AND PRACTICE, 2(4), 463-469. <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/mpttp/article/view/5192>
58. Muyiddinov Bekali Bahodir o'g'li. (2024). The coronation and campaigns of Alexander The Great. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(5), 400–412. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11222912>
59. Muyiddinov Bekali. (2024). COVERAGE OF LEGAL ISSUES IN "AVESTO". МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(6), 222–230. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12191420>
60. MUYIDDINOV BEKALI, & QORYOG'DIEV Z. (2022). ABOUT THE CONQUEST OF BUKHARA BY THE KHOREZMSHAHS. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 158–161. Retrieved from <https://www.ijpsss.iscience.uz/index.php/ijpsss/article/view/383>